

Pd nanoparticles immobilized on the poly-dopamine decorated halloysite nanotubes hybridized with N-doped porous carbon monolayer: A versatile catalyst for promoting Pd catalyzed reactions

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Abstract

A hybrid catalyst, Pd@Hal-pDA-NPC, with the utility for promoting both Csingle bondC coupling reactions (Sonogashira, Heck and Suzuki reactions) and hydrogenation of nitrocompounds is prepared through two main steps. First, Pd(0) nanoparticles was immobilized on the poly-dopamine decorated halloysite nanotubes (Hal-pDA) and then Pd@Hal-pDA was hybridized with the layers of a novel multi-N-doped porous carbon monolayer derived from 4,4',4''-((1,3,5-triazine-2,4,6-triyl)tris(azanediyl))tribenzonitrile. The results established that the catalyst could catalyze all the reactions efficiently under mild reaction condition. Moreover Pd@Hal-pDA-NPC exhibited high recyclability (up to ten reaction runs). Using various control catalysts, precise stuy was performed to elucidate the role of NPC and p-DA in the catalysis and suppressing Pd leaching. The results confirmed that both NPC and p-DA could improve Pd

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loading, while suppress its leaching. Moreover, it was proved that incorporation of NPC was more effective than graphitic carbon nitride, g-G3N4, and graphene oxide, GO.

Keywords: HalloysitePd, N-doped porous carbon, Dopamine, Heterogeneous catalysts